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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning

FEMaLe

Call/Topic: Digital transformation in Health and Care

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of I Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

WP9. BEACON: dissemination, communication, and synergies

D9.9 – Exploitation of results plan, M38

1. Exploitation strategy

By involving key stakeholders in the project's planning, execution, and dissemination, the FEMaLe Consortium ensures that the project's objectives and outcomes align with the needs and priorities of different end-users and that the project's results are communicated effectively to relevant stakeholders. This active engagement also contributes to the social and ethical responsibility of the FEMaLe project, as it fosters transparency, accountability, and trust between the project team and the wider community.

Table 1 shows the 18 FEMaLe advisers recruited and engaged since the beginning of the project.

#	Name	Representing	Label
1	Annalise Weckesser	Social Sciences Endometriosis Network, Birmingham University, UK	Research
2	Dorthe Hartwell	Dept. of Gynaecology, Copenhagen University Hospital, Denmark	Clinician
3	Engin Oral	Endometriosis and Adenomyosis Society, Turkey	Clinician
4	Francesco Mureddu	The Lisbon Council, Belgium	Policy
5	Harald Krentel	European Endometriosis League, Germany	Clinician
6	Maria Tomlinson	Dept. of Journalism Studies, The University of Sheffield, UK	Research
7	Marina Kvaskoff	National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), France	Research
8	Martin Götte	Dept. of Gynecology and Obstetrics, University of Münster, Germany	Research
9	Stacey Missmer	Michigan State University, the US	Research
10	Annemiek Nap	Radboud University and Radboudumc, The Netherlands	Clinician
11	Femke Jansen	World Endometriosis Organizations (WEO), UK	Research
12	Horace Roman	Endometriosis Center, Clinique Tivoli-Ducos, Bordeaux, France	Clinician
13	Bianca Schor	PhD student, Alan Turing Institute, Cambridge Computer Lab, UK	Research
14	Bharati Shivalkar	Delta (CHIREC) Hospital, Belgium	Clinician
15	Annemette Broch	DATA for GOOD Foundation, Denmark	IT / Tech
16	Katarina Olbers	Barnendometriosisfonden, Sweden	Policy
17	Louise Dreisig	Freelance Journalist, Denmark	Policy
18	Nora Salas Seoane	Science for Change, Spain	Policy

1. The Menstrual Movement in the Media: Reducing Stigma and Tackling Inequalities

In 2019, FEMaLe Adviser Dr Maria Tomlinson began her research project on the impact of the media and mediated menstrual activism on young people’s knowledge and perceptions of the health and social issues around menstruation. This included a research question about endometriosis: *How have the media and the menstrual movement influenced young people’s awareness of menstrual health issues such as endometriosis?*

2. The Method

Dr. Tomlinson conducted semi-structured focus groups with 58 female, 3 nonbinary, and 16 male participants in schools, colleges, and at a university across Yorkshire (UK), including questions related to endometriosis: *Have you read anything in newspapers/on social media about menstrual health? What about endometriosis?*

3. Research Findings

Out of the 77 teenagers (aged 16-19) who participated, 49 were unaware of endometriosis and 28 were aware, out of which 2 could accurately define endometriosis. Most of participants who were aware of endometriosis either had the condition or had learned about it from friends or family rather than via the media. Social media posts about endometriosis tend to only reach those who had already heard of the condition and were following feminist/endometriosis specific accounts. Very few participants were aware of activism around endometriosis and struggled to remember key messages. Participants had internalised misinformation about endometriosis; they believed that images of energetic, happy, and exercising women in period product adverts undermine and erase those who have endometriosis.

4. Participant-led Findings

Although participants were only asked questions about how endometriosis is represented in the media, they were given the space to lead the discussion and explore other aspects of endometriosis. Participants frequently changed the topic to the following three themes:

- A societal undermining of period pain; *"My cousin has endometriosis, it's quite common but it's not looked into. It makes women feel like they're being overdramatic".*
- The relationship between doctors and patients with period pain; *"Instead of trying to help, they put you on birth control to stop the pain instead of looking further into it".*
- Lack of education in schools about menstrual health and how to recognise if period pain requires medical intervention; *"Because there's not a lot of education on menstruation, you might feel that excessive pain is normal. But it's not supposed to be excessive and debilitating, which a lot of people don't realise".*

5. Knowledge exchange with FEMaLe Project

Due to Dr. Tomlinson's expertise in endometriosis, the social sciences, youth, social media, and inclusive research practices, she was appointed to the advisory board of FEMaLe. Since the FEMaLe project aims to improve intervention and treatment for those with endometriosis, we discussed reasons for why young people with endometriosis experience long delays before diagnosis.

6. Approaching findings from a new perspective

To respond to FEMaLe's questions about diagnosis, Dr. Tomlinson returned to the transcripts of her focus groups. She realised that the three main themes that emerged in participant-led discussions provided answers as to why young women and people with endometriosis wait many years for a diagnosis:

- They are reticent to discuss their menstrual pain for fear that others will undermine them e.g. by labelling them as 'overdramatic'.
- They are reluctant to discuss menstrual pain with doctors because of fears that they will not be believed or offered treatment (such as the contraceptive pill) that masks the cause of the pain, has unwanted side effects, or, in the case of nonbinary patients, conflicts with their gender identity.
- Society normalises strong period pain, adverts downplay the impact of pain, and students do not learn what level of pain is typical. Thus, young women and people who menstruate are unsure when to seek medical intervention.

7. Webinar: *Young People and Endometriosis: Social Perspectives on the Delay to Diagnosis*

Discovering that the delay to diagnosis was a recurrent theme in social science research conducted by scholars in the UK, Denmark, and Canada, we organised a joint webinar on 2nd February 2022.

8. *Future Cross-Cultural Collaborations*

During meetings with members of the FEMaLe research team in Aarhus (August 2022), we shared our experiences of conducting endometriosis research with young people. Moreover, we have discussed how Dr. Tomlinson's focus groups could be replicated in schools across Denmark, and this proposed project could compare young people's awareness of endometriosis and attitudes towards medical intervention across Europe.

2. Scientific outputs

a. The full-paper publications

Table 2 shows the ten scientific articles that have been published since the beginning of the project:

#	Title	Journal	Published	DOI
1	Des pistes de réflexion pour la recherche sur l'endométriose en France	<i>Med Sci (Paris)</i>	25 March, 2022	https://doi.org/10.1051/medsci/2022027
2	Temporal and regional differences in the incidence of hospital-diagnosed endometriosis: a Danish population-based study	<i>AOGS</i>	17 April, 2022	https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.14364
3	Psychological interventions improve quality of life despite persistent pain in endometriosis: results of a 3-armed RCT	<i>Quality of Life Research</i>	17 February, 2023	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-023-03346-9
4	The genetic basis of endometriosis and comorbidity with other pain and inflammatory conditions	<i>Nature Genetics</i>	13 March, 2023	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01323-z
5	Danish translation, cross-cultural adaptation, and electronic migration of the World Endometriosis Research Foundation Endometriosis Phenome and Biobanking Harmonisation Project Endometriosis Patient Questionnaire	<i>Front Glob Womens Health</i>	13 March, 2023	https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2023.1102006
6	The lived experiences of endometriosis in adolescence: A critical hermeneutic perspective	<i>Scand J Caring Sci.</i>	22 May, 2023	https://doi.org/10.1111/scs.13176
7	Utilisation of healthcare prior to endometriosis diagnosis: a Danish case-control study	<i>Human Reproduction</i>	October, 2023	https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dead164
8	Not 'just a bad period' – The impact of a co-created endometriosis social media health campaign: a mixed methods study	<i>Frontiers Commun.</i>	30 October, 2023	https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2023.1154297
9	FEMaLe: The Use of Machine Learning for Early Diagnosis of Endometriosis Based on Patient Self-reported Data – Study Protocol of a Multicenter Trial	<i>PLOS ONE</i>	8 December, 2023	Accepted for publication
10	Enhancing Surgery in Endometriosis Laparoscopy: Training Neural Networks to Segment Incision Boundaries	<i>Artificial Intelligence Surgery</i>	January, 2024	http://dx.doi.org/10.20517/ais.2024.02

b. Popularised publications

Table 3 shows the four popularised publication, which have been published so far in the project:

#	Title	Journal	Published	Link
1	Endometriosis: How advocacy, awareness and algorithms could shorten the long wait for diagnosis and treatment	<i>The Conversation Canada</i>	11 April, 2022	https://theconversation.com/endometriosis-how-advocacy-awareness-and-algorithms-could-shorten-the-long-wait-for-diagnosis-and-treatment-178591
2	Tallene er vilde, og det er mange kvinder, der bliver ramt af den her sygdom med hæslelige invaliderende smerter	<i>Politiken</i>	9 August, 2023	https://politiken.dk/debat/kroniken/art9408095/Tallene-er-vilde-og-det-er-mange-kvinder-der-bliver-ramt-af-den-her-sygdom-med-haeslelige-invaliderende-smerter
3	Kvinder har rent faktisk ret, når de siger, at lægen ikke lytter – ny forskning i endometriose sætter spot på et samfundsproblem	<i>Berlingske</i>	13 October, 2023	https://www.berlingske.dk/kronikker/kvinder-har-rent-faktisk-ret-naar-de-siger-at-laegen-ikke-lytter-ny
4	WORLD'S LARGEST ENDOMETRIOSIS STUDY NEEDS YOUR HELP	Semmelweis University	26 September, 2023	https://semmelweis.hu/english/2023/09/worlds-largest-endometriosis-study-needs-your-help/

c. Abstracts and attendance

Table 4 shows the 42 abstracts that have been submitted, accepted, and presented so far in the project:

WP	#	Title	Event	Type	Place & Date
1	1	How agile practices change over time in a large EU-funded research and innovation project	EURAM 2023	Oral	Dublin, Jun 2023
2	2	From smartphone supported Citizen Health Science to Cooperative Citizen Test Lab	AU Citizen Science 2022	Workshop	Aarhus, Apr 2022
	3	Endometriosis and Citizen Health Science: A New Future for Responsible Research and Innovation Priority Setting?	ECSA 2022	Poster	Berlin, Oct 2022
	4	Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: Citizen Science Experiences	Citizen Science i Midten	Workshop	Aarhus, Aug 2023
3	5	One Step Closer to the True Prevalence Of Endometriosis: Results Of A Delphi Study	WCE 2023	Poster	Edinburg, May 2023
	6	Endometriosis: Consequences of Delayed Diagnosis			
	7	Endometriosis: What research tells us	Closed Hearing in the Danish Parliament	Oral	Copenhagen, May 2023
	8	The Epidemiology of Endometriosis	Open Hearing in the Danish Parliament		Copenhagen, Nov 2023
4	9	Genetic Subtypes in Endometriosis Identified from Combinatorial Analytics	WCE 2023	Oral	Edinburg, May 2023
	10	The Genetic Basis of Endometriosis and Comorbidity with Other Pain and Inflammatory Conditions			
	11	Defining the Proteomic Profiles for Endometriosis Sub-types		Poster	
	12	From genes to mechanism in endometriosis	NCGE-NCE2023	Keynote	Middelfart, Jun 2023
	13	The Genetics of Endometriosis	Open Hearing in the Danish Parliament	Oral	Copenhagen, Nov 2023
	14	Endometriosis: What research tells us	Open Seminar in the European Parliament		Brussels, Nov 2023
5	15	The Use of the Lucy App in Patient Profiling for Early Diagnosis of Endometriosis	WCE 2023	Oral	Edinburg, May 2023
	16	Hey Lucy! Your best friend on hard days! Period tracker/menstruation calendar mobile application for the early recognition of menstrual diseases		Poster	
	17	Lucy application in the FEMaLe study	6th Meeting of Young Endoscopic Gynaecologists	Oral	Pecs, Oct 2023
	18	The FEMaLe project and the Lucy application	6 th Health 2.0 Hungary Chapter Meeting	Oral	Budapest, Nov 2023
	19	Management of Endometriosis	Ethicon CEE Live Webinar	Oral	Online, Nov 2023

	20	The FEMaLe project and the Lucy application	EEL Masterclass	Oral	Budapest, Dec 2023
6	21	Integration of health initiatives with tools and services under the European Open Science Cloud (LETHE, FEMaLe and HealthyCloud)	EGI 2022	Workshop	Prague, Sept 2022
	22	Applying Cross-Border Machine Learning Approach for GDPR-protected Medical Data	WCE 2023	Poster	Edinburg, May 2023
7	23	Recognition of Endometriosis in Laparoscopy by AI: Achieving a Methodological Consensus	WCE 2023	Poster	Edinburg, May 2023
	24	Endometriosis and Surgery: How AI can help?	Open Seminar in the European Parliament	Oral	Brussels, Nov 2023
	25	Enhancing Surgery in Endometriosis Laparoscopy: Training Neural Networks to Segment Incision Boundaries	Surgical AI day		Ghent, Dec 2023
8	26	Developing a Digital Mindfulness- and Acceptance-based Intervention for Endometriosis Management	WCE 2023	Oral	Edinburg, May 2023
	27	Women with endometriosis experiences of receiving a digital mindfulness- and acceptance-based intervention for endometriosis management		Poster	
	28	Is Therapist Guidance Important to the Outcome Of A Digital Endometriosis Self-Management Programme? A Three-Armed RCT	NCGE-NCE2023	Poster	Middelfart, Jun 2023
	29	Is Therapist Guidance Important to the Outcome Of A Digital Endometriosis Self-Management Programme? A Three-Armed RCT			
9	30	It makes women feel like they're overdramatic: The Influence of Social Norms and Media on Young People's Perceptions of Endometriosis	ECREA 2022	Poster	Aarhus, Oct 2022
	31	The Role of Social Media in Endometriosis Care	WCE 2023	Poster	Edinburg, May 2023
	32	Successful Engagement of Public and Patients in EU-funded Research Projects			
	33	Impact of Social Relations in Reducing Stigma Among Women Living With Endometriosis			
	34	Endometriosis: What are the asks from patients?	Open Seminar in the European Parliament	Oral	Brussels, Nov 2023
	35	Call-To-Action: movements in endometriosis			
10	36	A bird's-eye view of the FEMaLe project	EEL 2022	Oral	Bordeaux, June 2022
	37	Endometriosis: The Basic Facts	Representation in the Danish Parliament	Oral	Copenhagen, March 2023
	38	Endometriosis and National Actions Plans	Closed Hearing in the Danish Parliament		Copenhagen, May 2023
	39	A bird's-eye view of the FEMaLe project	NCGE-NCE2023	Keynote	Middelfart, Jun 2023
	40	A bird's-eye view of the FEMaLe project	Medicon Valley Alliance		Copenhagen, Oct 2023
	41	Endometriosis and National Actions Plans	Open Hearing in the Danish Parliament	Oral	Copenhagen, Nov 2023
	42	Endometriosis: The Basic Facts	Open Seminar in the European Parliament		Brussels, Nov 2023

3. Innovation outputs

Throughout the FEMaLe project, the innovations developed will mature and their Technical Readiness Level (TRL) will increase.

Table 5 shows the list of FEMaLe WPs that are associated with innovation action:

WP	Title	Lead
4	OMICS: risk classifier and biological subtypes	UOXF
5	BIG DATA: digital health monitoring and the Lucy App	SWU
6	DIAGNOSIS: surgical phenotyping using machine learning	RTU
7	VISUAL: augmented reality to improve laparoscopic surgery	SURG
8	DIGITAL: self-management program	YLK

Table 6 shows the list of FEMaLe WPs that are associated with innovation/technology outputs as well as their corresponding and expected TRL at this time point of the project:

WP	Technology / Innovation	TRL 07 2022	TRL 03 2023	TRL 01 2024	Expected Final TRL
4	2 prototypes of CDS tools: risk stratification and multi-marker	2	3	4	5
5	Lucy app	7	8	8	9
5	A prototype of a dietary and lifestyle module	4	5	7	7
5	A prototype of a global risk profile	1	1	2	5
6	Software implementing a machine learning based algorithm for the detection and scoring of endometriosis	3	3	4	5
7	Software implementing a machine learning-based algorithm for the suggestion of endometriotic resection zone	2	2	3	4
8	Implementation of program into modified Lucy app	3	3	4	5

4. Exploitation of outputs

The FEMaLe partners host and participate in several events to disseminate all the project's results.

4.1 Multiplier events organised and conducted by the FEMaLe project.

Table 7 shows a selected few key multiplier events hosted by the FEMaLe project:

Multiplier Event	Type	Date	Venue
Budapest-Vienna Bike Fundraiser	Awareness raising: Public Fundraiser	26 March 2021	Austria and Hungary
Balaton Bike Fundraiser	Awareness raising: Public Fundraiser	10-19 June 2021	Hungary
Richter Health Town Appearances	Awareness raising	March 2021	Hungary
Virtual Running Fundraiser	Awareness raising: Public Fundraiser	1-31 July 2021	Hungary
Richter Health Town Appearances	Awareness raising	September 2021	Hungary
FEMaLe Project Case Competition: Project Management and Health	Education / Teaching	15 October 2021	Aarhus, Denmark
Young People and Endometriosis: Social Perspectives on the Delay to Diagnosis	Joint webinar	2 February 2022	Online
FEMaLe Project & Danish Endometriosis Patient Association Campaign	Awareness raising: Social Media	March 2022	Online
Half Double and Public Health Research	Research workshop	29 April 2022	Aarhus, Denmark
Richter Health Town Appearances	Awareness raising	May & June 2022	Hungary
FEMaLe, Science for Change and the TRANSFORM Project	Joint webinar	13 October 2022	Online
FEMaLe Project & Endometriosis UK	Instagram LIVE & Joint webinar	November 2022	Online
FEMaLe Project & Endometriosis.org	Awareness raising: Glossary	February 2023	Online
FEMaLe Project & Danish Endometriosis Patient Association Campaign	Awareness raising: Social Media	March 2023	Online
FEMaLe Project & Giv De Unge Ordet	Research workshop	March 2023	Aarhus, Denmark
FEMaLe Project & World Endometriosis Organisations	Joint webinar	12 April 2023	Online
FEMaLe Project & Swedish Endometriosis Patient Association Campaign	Awareness raising: Social Media	December 2023	Online
FEMaLe Project hosts the esteemed endometriosis expert Grant Montgomery	Research visit	December 2023	Denmark

Social media continues to be an important sphere for healthcare communication and an ideal place for activist agendas within the health domain. It is often utilised by health organisations to raise awareness, promote actions, address health problems, or advocate for change in public policies related to health issues. An example of this is the endometriosis social media health campaign (#1in10 campaign) by the Danish Endometriosis Patient Association (DEPA).

In the summer of 2021, DEPA launched the first series of the #1in10 campaign on Facebook and Instagram. The campaign was led by a Danish journalist, who was herself a patient with endometriosis. It was designed as an informational campaign to convey the struggles of living with endometriosis. In the creation of the #1in10 campaign, DEPA reached out to their members with endometriosis to engage them in a co-creation process. They were asked to submit a photograph of themselves and formulate a question based on their own experiences with endometriosis. Questions included: 'Why must I live in constant pain?' or 'Why is my disease not being taken seriously?' Each social media post then consisted of one photograph, the name and age of the woman in the photograph, and her question. Following the first release of the campaign in 2021, a second series was released later that year, with a total of 25 different patient submissions being posted.

In 2022 the FEMaLe project entered a collaboration with DEPA to translate 15 of the patient questions into English and visually redesign the campaign to fit FEMaLe's visual identity and guidelines for co-branding. It was then promoted through FEMaLe's social media accounts on Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn, as part of the worldwide endometriosis awareness month of March 2022.

4.2 External events with FEMaLe project participation.

Table 8 shows a selected few key external events with FEMaLe project participation:

Event	Type	Date	Venue
Introducing the FEMaLe Project	Facebook Live	25 March 2021	Online (Denmark)
Radio and TV spots	Awareness raising	March 2021	Hungary
Libresse Pain Dictionary	Awareness raising	23 September – 14 October 2021	Hungary
UK Endometriosis and Pelvic Pain Network	Annual meeting	23 September 2021	Warwick, UK
Danish Endometriosis Patient Association	Annual meeting	2 October 2021	Aarhus, Denmark
Machine Learning and Augmented Reality	EEL Special webinar	15 December 2021	Online
Consumer Electronics Show	Industry conference	6 January 2022	Las Vegas & Online
Radio and TV spots	Awareness raising	March 2022	Hungary
Engaging Citizen Science Conference	Scientific conference	25-26 April 2022	Aarhus, Denmark
12 th Congress of European Pain Federation	Scientific conference	29 April 2022	Dublin, Ireland
Lady Walk	Awareness raising	30 May 2022	Denmark
6 th European Congress on Endometriosis	Awareness raising: Scientific conference	15-17 June 2022	Bordeaux, France
European Citizen Science Conference	Scientific conference	5-8 October 2022	Berlin, Germany
9 th European Communication Conference	Scientific conference	19-22 October 2022	Aarhus, Denmark
Danish Ministry of the Interior and Health's Health Committee	Policy briefing	2 March 2023	Copenhagen, Denmark (Danish Parliament)
15 th World Congress on Endometriosis	Scientific conference	3-6 May 2023	Edinburgh, Scotland
Lady Walk	Awareness raising	22 May 2023	Denmark
Danish Ministry of the Interior and Health's Health Committee	Closed expert hearing	25 May 2023	Copenhagen, Denmark (Danish Parliament)
NCGE-NCE2023 Congress	Scientific conference	1-3 June 2023	Middelfart, Denmark
EURAM 2023 Annual Conference	Scientific conference	14-16 June 2023	Dublin, Ireland
FEMaLe & Innovation News Network	Awareness raising	September 2023	Online
MVA's Women's Health Network	Awareness raising	3 October 2023	Copenhagen, Denmark
Danish Ministry of the Interior and Health's Health Committee	Public open hearing	15 November 2023	Copenhagen, Denmark (Danish Parliament)
Financing Innovation in Women's Health	Catenion report	22 November 2023	Online
For the life of women – in the shadow of endometriosis	Open Seminar	29 November 2023	European Parliament, Brussels, Belgium

Table 9 shows a list of relevant events and conferences for FEMaLe participation in 2024:

Event	Date	Venue
10 th SEUD Congress	18-20 April 2024	Geneva, Switzerland
7 th European Endometriosis Congress	6-8 June 2024	Bucharest, Romania
40 th Annual Meeting of ESHRE	7-10 July 2024	Amsterdam, The Netherlands

5. Business exploitation plan

This section includes business ideas related to the innovative solutions developed under WP4-WP8:

WP4 | OMICS: risk classification and subtypes

Two prototypes of CDS tools (risk stratification and multi-marker signature).

WP5 | BIG DATA: digital health monitoring and the Lucy App

Lucy app, including prototype of the dietary and lifestyle modules as well as prototype of a global risk profile.

WP6 | DIAGOSIS: machine learning automatic surgical phenotyping.

Software implementing a machine learning-based algorithm for the detection and scoring of endometriosis.

WP7 | VISUAL: laparoscopic surgery using augmented reality.

Software implementing a machine learning-based algorithm for the suggestion of endometriotic resection zone.

WP8 | DIGITAL: self-management program

Digital mental health program (MY-ENDO) translated, validated, and implemented into the modified Lucy app.

In devising our business exploitation plan, we have been leveraging market trends and consumer behavior to maximise profits and growth. First, we have conducted market research with end-users – particularly patients and surgeons – to identify emerging niches and underserved segments (as an initial example, see D6.4). Utilising data analytics and consumer insights, we have tailored FEMaLe's innovative solutions to meet the specific needs and preferences of these target audiences. Our marketing strategy has already been focusing on creating compelling and engaging campaigns across various channels, including social media, influencers, and strategic partnerships. Moreover, we will optimise our pricing strategy to ensure competitiveness while maximising profitability. By continuously monitoring market dynamics and adapting our approach accordingly, we aim to establish a strong market presence and drive sustainable revenue growth over the long term.

6. Citizen-arena exploitation plan

Table 10 shows a list of 26 endometriosis organisations relevant for FEMaLe project in Europe.

No.	Name of the organisation	Country
1	Asociația Eu și Endometrioza	Romania
2	Asociacion de Afectadas de Endometriosis de Madrid (ADAEM)	Spain
3	Asociacion de Endometriosis España (AEE)	Spain
4	Associazione Italiana Endometriosi Onlus (AIE)	Italy
5	Associazione Progetto Endometriosi Onlus (APE)	Italy
6	“Együtt könnyebb” Női Egészségért Alapítvány	Hungary
7	EndoFrance	France
8	EndoTalks	Czech Republic
9	Endometriosisyhdistys ry	Finland
10	Endometrioseforeningen	Norway
11	Endometriose Fællesskabet	Denmark
12	Endometrioseföreningen	Sweden
13	EndoHome – Endometriosis Association Belgium	Belgium
14	Endometriosis and Reproductive Health Foundation	Bulgaria
15	Endometriosis Association of Ireland	Ireland
16	Endometriosis Catalunya	Spain
17	Endometriosis South Coast	United Kingdom
18	Endometriose Stichting	The Netherlands
19	Endometriosis UK	United Kingdom
20	Endometriose-Vereinigung Deutschland e.V.	Germany
21	ENDOmIND	France
22	EVA – Endometriose Vereinigung Austria	Austria
23	MulherEndo (Associação Portuguesa de Apoio a Mulheres com Endometriose)	Portugal
24	Pierwszy Polski Portal o Endometriozie	Poland
25	Samtök um Endómetríósu	Iceland
26	Turkish Endometriosis & Adenomyosis Society	Turkey